

Retracted article: Two stones for one bird: Parental involvement among teacher couples during the modular distance learning

Alfredo C. Padios Jr., John Keeneth M. Ferrera, Teresita T. Rungduin

Abstract

The article entitled “*Two stones for one bird: Parental involvement among teacher couples during the modular distance learning*” (Volume 4, Issue 1, December 2022, pp. 61-72) written by Alfredo C. Padios Jr., John Keeneth M. Ferrera, and Teresita T. Rungduin has been retracted at the request of the Corresponding Author. Moreover, the affiliation of the Corresponding Author, Alfredo C. Padios Jr., has been updated and corrected.

Alfredo C. Padios Jr.*

Aurora State College of Technology, Baler, Aurora, Philippines

John Keeneth M. Ferrera

President Diosdado Macapagal High School, Taguig City, Philippines

Teresita T. Rungduin

Philippine Normal University, Manila, Philippines

*Corresponding author's email address:

alfredopadios@ascot.edu.ph

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